

Fiscal Policy Shocks and Industrial Sector Output Growth in Nigeria: A Structural Vector Error Correction (SVEC) Approach

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Abstract

This study estimated Nigeria's fiscal policy shock and industrial productivity growth between 1980 and 2022. The study employed varied methodologies including Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), Phillip Peron (PP), and Structural Vector Error Correction (SVEC) to ascertain the interactions amongst the macroeconomic indicators. The result shows that government spending exhibits a significant negative relationship with the industrial sector in Nigeria, though there was evidence of fiscal sustainability. The Nigerian industrial sector output responds positively to government revenue shock. The IRF and the FEVD results corroborated the SVEC result that the government expenditure shock has negative effect on the Nigerian industrial sector output growth. The implication is that fiscal policy shock to government revenue and expenditure were not significant determinants of the variation in the Nigerian industrial sector growth in the short and long run. Apart from the aggregate supply shock, aggregate demand shock to general price and investment shock to capital formation are the major determinants of Nigerian industrial sector growth variation in the short, medium, and long runs. Finally, Capital formation is a significant determinant of industrial sector growth in Nigeria, as capital has positive and persistent impact on the industrial sector output. It is recommended that economically friendly fiscal policies be implemented for the Nigerian industrial sector to experience growth. The revenue generated should be channelled to the real sectors of the economy to enhance industrial output growth. Monetary authorities may manage inflation and interest rates within the threshold that will enhance productivity in industrial sectors.

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I. Introduction

The use of fiscal policy as a stabilization tool gained more attention after the great depression of the 1930s (Barro & Sala-i-Martin, 1992). After the bubbles and bursts in the stock market and the Great Depression of 1930s, there was an advocacy for increased government participation in the economy (Horton *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, fiscal policy was fronted to play the arbitration role as one of the macroeconomic measures to catalyze the economy and stabilize macroeconomic indicators, such as achieving sustainable economic growth, maintaining a low level of inflation, and a low unemployment rate among others (Agu & Nyatanga, 2020).

Over the years, Nigerian government has been engaging in different fiscal policy measures; both contractionary and expansionary. These have created a lot of macroeconomic shocks in the economy, leading to the adjustment of various macroeconomic variables and sudden changes in output growth. Despite all those fiscal interventions, the industrial sector of Nigeria has not witnessed a significant growth (World Bank, 2023).

Nigeria's industrial sector share of GDP has been progressively declining on average over the past three decades while the government revenues and expenditures have consistently risen. For example, in 1981, the industrial sector's share of GDP peaked at 39.2%. From 1995 to 2000, it declined from 36.5% to 33.8%. It became the lowest in 2016 with 18.17%, though it increased from 22.2% to 23.9% between 2017 and 2022 but the increase was insignificant (World Bank, 2023). On the other hand, government spending and revenue have been averagely increasing over the years. Government revenue increased by 11.8% between 1981 and 1988 and further increased markedly by about 27.3% by the end of 2005. From 2006 to 2022, government revenue increased by about 14.7% (CBN, 2023). Also, between 1981 and 1986, government expenditure increased by about 5.8% and further increased by about 30% by the end of 1999. Between 2000 and 2022, government expenditure increased by about 15.6% (CBN, 2023). Comparatively, between 1981 and 2022, the government revenue growth rate has been revolving between 31% and 95.21% while government expenditure growth rate has been fluctuating between 33.74% and 76.36%, but industrial sector output growth rate has been between 2.36% and 39.2% (CBN, 2023).

Various policies and program have been put in place by the governments to accelerate the Nigerian industrial sector growth. For instance, the import-substituting industrialization policy of 1962 was set up and this period witnessed the huge government's capital investment projects such as the Ughelli thermal plants and the Kanji dam to provide infrastructural stamina for the emerging industrial sector. Also, during this period, the bulk of the government revenue which was mainly generated from the agriculture proceeds was used to develop industrial take-off catalyzing infrastructures. Such infrastructure were petroleum refineries, iron and steel companies and so on (Chete *et al.*, 2014). In addition, during the second national development plan (1970-74), government engaged in white elephant industrial projects such as pulp and paper, cement, sugar, and fertilizer industries among others through the public sector-led industrialization policy. The third national development plan (1975-80) gulped the outlay of about \$42 billion, emphasizing public sector investment in the industry, particularly the heavy industries (Oyelaran, 1997).

Following the shortcomings of the national development plans to yield the needed industrial output revolution, the structural adjustment policy of 1986 was introduced to promote economic development. During this period, government expenditure was reoriented and taxes on consumer goods were increased to stabilize the economy (Chete et al., 2014). Other policies that were established by the government to encourage industrial output growth were: trade and financial liberalization of 1989, the Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) of 1990 and the Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIES) in 2000. Also among the policies were: the Fiscal Policies Act 2019, Furthermore, the Fiscal Policies Act 2020 (Finance Act 2020), which took effect on January 1, 2021, included provisions for a COVID-19 fiscal stimulus by establishing a Crisis Intervention Fund which was geared towards meeting any exigencies that may arise as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic (BOFIA, 2020).

All these efforts by the government were purposely adopted to enhance the tax base, provide incentives for small enterprises by lowering their tax burdens, and improve domestic production through the excise duties mechanism. It was also aimed at helping industrial firms expand faster by providing long-term loans, equity financing, and technical support, to boost investment in industries, to restrict the importation and consumption of particular commodities through tariffs. All these policies were to encourage industrial output growth and to achieve stable and sustainable economic growth among other things (Chete et al., 2014; BOFIA, 2020; Yomi et al., 2019)

The concept of the positive elastic impact of government expenditure on output, known as the fiscal stabilization concept, will be adopted in this study to investigate the extent to which government expenditure has impacted the industrial sector in Nigeria. The conventional new Keynesian model predicts that a positive spending shock will raise employment, wages, and consumption. Standard neoclassical models, on the other hand, noted that after a positive government expenditure shock, private consumption and real wages would decline due to the negative wealth effect. The available empirical data for advanced economies tend to support either viewpoint (see Blanchard & Perotti, 2002). However, in less developed nations like Nigeria, such transmission systems may not be as successful. For instance, the wealth effect requires a developed financial market, but in less developed countries like Nigeria, financial markets are often not sufficiently developed. Therefore, whether exogenous government spending shock on the Nigerian industrial sector stimulates productivity or dampens it is one of the questions to which this study proposed to answer. Also, the question of whether revenue shock should have a negative or positive influence on the industrial sector output remains a puzzle in the literature.

Some scholars uphold that a positive tax shock would enhance the provision of an enabling environment for output growth (Akintoye & Tashie, 2013; Eluyela et al., 2018a). On the other hand, some scholars such as Barro & Sala-i-Martin, 1992; Chen et al., (2017) and Perotti (2005) noted that raising the tax rate to generate more revenue in the short run may have a negative impact on households' disposable incomes, reduce capital accumulation, and discourage investment and output growth, since a larger proportion of businesses' gross profits are paid in taxes thereby causing the aggregate

demand to fall in the long run. These dilemmas are the crux this study intends to investigate.

There are cooperative interactions between fiscal and monetary policies. For example, expansionary fiscal policy and expansionary monetary policy can stimulate economic growth, increase aggregate demand, and boost industrial production. While contractionary fiscal policy and contractionary monetary policy can reduce inflation, decrease aggregate demand, and slow industrial growth (BOFIA, 2020; Yomi et al., 2019).

There are also conflictive interactions between the two policy tools. For instance, expansionary fiscal policy and contractionary monetary policy may lead to higher interest rates, reduce investment, and decrease industrial growth. While, contractionary fiscal policy and expansionary monetary policy may result in reduced government revenue, decreased public investment, and lower industrial growth.

Fiscal and monetary policies affect industrial growth through various channels, including interest rates. Monetary policy influences interest rates, affecting borrowing costs and investment decisions. It can also influence aggregate demand through fiscal policy which impacts aggregate demand, influences industrial production and growth. Exchange rates and monetary policy affect exchange rates, impacting export competitiveness and industrial growth. Fiscal policy influences public investment, while monetary policy affects private investment decisions (Chete et al., 2014).

Extensive studies have been carried out on the impact of monetary policy shocks on industrial/manufacturing sector output in Nigeria; however, the effect of fiscal policy shocks has received limited empirical attention. Few studies have been done in the area of fiscal shock in Nigeria (see Akpan & Atan, 2015; Attahir, 2016). Further, the standard econometric workhorse that is usually adopted in analyzing the effect of fiscal policy shocks in Nigeria is the Structural Vector Auto-Regressive (SVAR) approach (Akpan & Atan, 2015; Attahir, 2016). However, some studies like Attahir (2016) and Oseni (2018) have shown that output variables and fiscal policy variables cointegrate invalidates the of SVAR technique. The Structural Vector Error Correction (SVEC) model is more appropriate and flexible for cointegrated and stationary variables while conducting structural analysis (Pagan & Pesaran, 2008). Therefore, most of the results in the existing studies on this subject are likely to suffer bias given that the variables included in the model are integrated and cointegrated. In this study, SVEC model was used to resolve this challenge and the suitable identification method was used to identify the fiscal policy shocks and hence estimate their influence on the industrial sector output growth.

The subsequent sections are structured thus: Section II presents the relevant literature review. Sections III and IV present data and methodology and discussion of the findings respectively while section V presents the conclusion and recommendations.

II. Relevant Literature Review

Some of the related literature on fiscal policy shocks is chronologically reviewed below. Yifei (2021) studied the macroeconomic influence of government expenditure shocks in New Zealand. Using seasonally adjusted quarterly data on government consumption, government investment, net tax, real GDP, inflation rate, interest rate, real effective exchange rate, private consumption and investment from 1991q1-2019q4, he estimated a recursive identified SVAR model. His study showed that GDP positively responds to both government spending and investment shocks, but the multiplier effect of government investment shock is larger than that of government consumption shock. The study also revealed that positive government spending shocks caused the New Zealand exchange rate to appreciate which is in line with the classical theory. There was a decrease in private spending and private investment after government expenditure shocks but reacted positively to government investment shocks.

Hammed and Arawomo (2020) investigated the influence of oil price and fiscal policy shocks on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Their study used yearly data on manufacturing sector output, oil price, total government expenditure, total government revenue, and inflation rate from 1981 to 2019 to estimate a recursively identified Structural Vector Auto Regressive (SVAR) model. Their study showed that the manufacturing sector and revenue shock are inversely related in the first period but has a positive relationship after the second period. The result also showed that expenditure shock had a cyclical effect on the manufacturing sector output; the immediate impact is negative but switches from positive to negative repeatedly afterwards. Price shock is shown to have an immediate positive effect on manufacturing sector output and the afterwards effects are insignificant. Oil price shock was shown to have an insignificant effect on manufacturing sector output. In the variance decomposition analysis, the study revealed that the government expenditure shock contributed mostly to the variation in manufacturing sector output initially but was the second-largest contributor apart from the manufacturing sector productivity shock in the long run. Total revenue shock contributed insignificantly to variation in manufacturing sector output.

Yunanto and Medyawati (2020) examined the contribution of fiscal policy shocks to the industrial sector in Indonesia. Their study used quarterly historical data on government expenditure, tax revenue, interest rate, consumer price index, and industrial sector GDP from 1999q1-2019q4. Their study employed the vector error correction model (VECM) after finding evidence of two cointegrating vectors among the variables. The impulse response analysis of their study showed that industrial sector productivity and tax are positively related to price index shocks. On the contrary, the industrial sector responds negatively to government spending and interest rate shocks. The forecast error variance decomposition result showed that government spending shock contributed the largest variation in industrial sector output compared to the other variables in the model.

Molumby and Skjæveland (2020) studied the impact of fiscal shocks in a small open economy using Norway as a case study. Their study utilized quarterly data on per capita real GDP, taxes, government spending, private consumption, and private investment from 1978q1-2017q4. They employed the SVAR econometric technique and adopted both the sign and recursive identification approaches as a means of robust analysis. Under the signed-restricted SVAR model result, their study showed that real per capita

GDP responds positively to government spending shock although insignificant in the short run. Also, real per capita GDP responds negatively to tax shock with a significant effect on impact but transitory; however, including private investment and consumption into the model shows that GDP and tax shock exhibit positive relationship. Counterintuitively, results from both models showed that while private consumption and investment are inversely related to spending shocks, and they are positively related to tax shocks.

Marsimoe (2019) examined the dynamic impacts of fiscal policy shocks on macroeconomic indicators in Ethiopia. The study used quarterly data on total government expenditure, total tax revenue, interest rate, real GDP, and inflation rate from 2000q1-2017q4. He employed both the VECM and SVAR estimating approaches. The result shows that government expenditure shock and output are significant and possess a positive relationship though at the expense of increased inflation, as well as a delayed positive effect on the interest rate. Also, in the short and long runs, the response of output to tax revenue shock was shown to be negative, as predicted by the theory. The study also shows that tax shock had a positive impact on inflation and interest rates.

Employing data set from 1986 to 2015, Abdulrasheed (2017) examined the causality amid government expenditure and revenue in Nigeria. The study employed cointegration technique and the VEC model as econometric tool of analysis. The study showed that there exists a cointegration nexus between government expenditure and revenue and that a one percent point increase in government revenue brought about a 44% rise in government expenditure. The result of the VEC-based Granger causality further shows that government expenditure Granger causes government revenue but not vice versa. However, despite this study adopting a cointegration-based technique, The study did not analyze the structural shock but only the direction of Granger causality and the long-run causal relationship.

Attahir (2016) analyzed the impacts of fiscal policy shocks on productivity and unemployment in Nigeria. The study employed annual data on unemployment rate, real GDP, public expenditure, and total revenue from 1981 to 2015. Despite finding one cointegrating vector among the variables using the Johansen technique, he proceeded to estimate a recursive identified SVAR model. His analysis showed that the public spending shock has a positive and lasting effect on output. Also, like the public spending shock, his result showed that output responds positively to tax shock but with a lower magnitude than that of the public expenditure shock. The study further showed that the unemployment rate responds negatively to tax shock but positively to expenditure shock.

In Nigeria, the macroeconomic impacts of a shock to the fiscal policy were studied by Akpan and

Atan (2015). Their research employed quarterly data from 1980 Q1 to 2010 Q4 on government consumption spending, real output, inflation rate, real interest rates, and private investment to estimate a recursive identified SVAR model. Their result showed that, although it tends to result in greater inflation in the short term, the shock to government capital spending on social and community programs have a significant positive influence on private spending and real output. Although theoretically consistent, their study showed that real output responds negatively to business tax

shock, but the effect is insignificant. Also, it was shown that private investment did not respond to government revenue shock but to interest rate shock.

Using quarterly data from 1983 Q1 to 2010 Q2, Parkyn and Vehbi (2013) examined the macroeconomic implications of fiscal policy in New Zealand. The variables included real GDP per capita, real net taxes, real government expenditure per capita, inflation rate, government gross debt, and interest rate. In this analysis, Blanchard and Perotti's (2002) enhanced five-variable SVAR technique was used to analyze the dynamic responses of production, inflation, and interest rates to fiscal shocks. They discovered in their research that shocks to government expenditure increased output in the short run but decreased it in the medium to long term. However, they discovered the perplexing effects of tax shock on the variables. Their study's historical decomposition analysis demonstrates that over the years, negative fiscal policy shocks have typically had a procyclical effect on the New Zealand economy. Additionally, the economy of New Zealand has had a positive but slight effect on inflation from the positive fiscal policy shock. However, the conventional SVAR approach they adopted might not be able to account for precisely the response of the variables to fiscal shocks because there is the possibility of a long-run relationship between government spending and tax variables and the GDP.

III. Data and Methodology

Theoretical Framework

The scope of this study is between 1980 and 2022, this period witnessed a lot of policy changes that caused severe shocks in the economy. This study relied on the endogenous growth framework of Barro & Salai-Martin (1992) which assumed a constant returns to scale. Broad capital can be decomposed into physical and government capital. Also, the model assumes that the public sector provides public services to each household agent and this expenditure is financed through tax income (Barro & Sala-i-Martin, 1992). It is also believed that growth is driven by the system operating within the economy rather than by factors outside the system (Todaro & Smith, 2003). Therefore, with public capital and taxes, public expenditure would positively impact the steady state and short-run growth. Hence, this theory is applicable to the study.

The model begins by maximizing the utility function, equation (1) of an infinitely lived representative consumer, and using the iso-elastic consumption function as shown in equation (2).

$$U = \int_0^{\infty} u[C(t)] e^{-\rho t} dt \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$C(t) = \frac{[c(t)^{1-\sigma}-1]}{1-\sigma} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

In equation (1), ρ is the subjective rate of time preference, and in equation (2), σ is the constant elasticity of substitution. Where u and σ represent the private capital and publicly provided capital respectively. It is also assumed that the representative producer produces output (y) according to the production function;

$$y(t) = A(t)^\alpha g(t)^\beta \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

In equation (3), α represents returns to private capital while β represents returns to public capital. The total factor productivity is depicted as the constant A . It is assumed that government operates a balanced budget each year through floating proportionate taxes on output (y) at the rate ($\tau = t/y$) and lump-sum taxes per individual of g . The government budget constraint is given as follows;

$$\varphi_{it} = \partial + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_i Y_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^n \epsilon_j X_{jt} + t ; t = \theta^{-1} w_t \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Therefore, equation (4) now expresses industrial output growth as a function of non-fiscal variables, Y_{it} , and the fiscal variables, X_{jt} .

Model Specification

Following the theoretical framework and modifying Kneller et al. (1999) model who stated that industrial output is determined by the government activities and the business environment forces, and decomposing Equation (4), the functional model is specified as;

$$IND = f(GOVR, GOVE, CPI, INT, KAP) \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where IND is industrial output; $GOVR$ is government revenue $GOVE$ is government expenditure; CPI is the consumer price index, as used by Agu & Nyatanga (2020); INT is the interest rate and KAP is the physical capital used in production, as used by Molumby and Skjæveland (2020). The data for Industrial Output (IND), Government Revenue (GOVR), and Government Expenditure (GOVE), as used by Abdulrasheed (2017) were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). In addition, the Consumer Price Index (CPI), Interest Rate (INT), and Capital (KAP), as used by Attahir (2016) were sourced from the World Bank database.

The SVEC Model Justification

The underlying econometrics technique to analyze the fiscal policy shocks is anchored on Structural Vector Error Correction (SVEC) approach. The SVEC model, unlike the SVAR model, accounts for cointegration among the variables. Moreover, unlike in the SVAR, the identification in the SVEC model is a generalized and extended form comprised of long-run and short-run restrictions. In addition, it is flexible to accommodate stationary endogenous variables (Pagan & Pesaran, 2008). The first part of the estimation procedure of the SVEC model is the generalized VEC model thus;

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \log ind_t \\ \Delta \log govr_t \\ \Delta int_t \\ \Delta \log gove_t \\ \Delta cpi_t \\ \Delta \log kap_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} \\ a_{51} & a_{52} & a_{53} \\ a_{61} & a_{62} & a_{63} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \beta_{14} & 0 & \beta_{16} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \beta_{24} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \beta_{35} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} ind_{t-1} \\ govr_{t-1} \\ goveint_{t-1} \\ gove_{t-1} \\ cpi_{t-1} \\ kap_{t-1} \end{bmatrix} + \sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i \Delta Z_{T-1} + v_t \dots \dots (6)$$

Equation (6) shows the baseline VEC system of log industrial output (ind), log government revenue (govr), log government expenditure (gove), interest rate (int), consumer price index (cpi), and log capital (kap). The alpha matrix has the adjustment coefficients, and the beta matrix has the cointegrating parameters. The vector Z represents the vector of variables and the last expression in the equation is the vector of shocks. Further, the first beta row shows an output-capital relationship; government expenditure either directly or indirectly influences industrial sector production. The second row corresponds to the government solvency rule (fiscal rule) and the estimate of β_{24} is expected to be positive and greater than one; else, government is considered to be insolvent. The last row in the vector corresponds to the fisher relation with the nominal interest rate and hence the value β_{35} is expected to be positive.

IV. Results and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Variables' descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max.	Min.	J-B Prob.
Ind	12149.940	2497.893	17.512	12.141	0.296
Govr	3606.400	3938.331	21.629	1.017	0.088
Gove	2250.882	2819.831	10164.560	9.637	0.002
Cpi	68.152	83.638	329.983	0.489	0.000
Int	17.454	4.603	29.800	7.750	0.601
Kap	861.876	200.443	1578.967	566.887	0.000

Source: Research finding 2024

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics. The first column shows the average values for the variables and it is all positive. The second column displays the standard deviation which depicts the relative dispersion of the variables. It can be deduced from the standard deviations that the interest rate has the least variation whereas the government revenue has the largest variation. The Jarque-Bera probability values for government revenue, government spending, consumer price index, and capital are significant at the conventional levels and this signifies that they are not normally distributed. However, the Jarque-Bera test statistics for the industrial output and interest rate are insignificant implying that they are normally distributed. By this, the model contains mixed distribution variables. Notwithstanding, the law of large numbers suggests that estimators converge to their population values asymptotically as the sample size increases.

Correlation matrix

Table 2: Correlation matrix

Variables	ind	govr	Gove	Cpi	int	kap
Ind	1					
govr	0.311***	1				
gove	0.403***	0.343***	1			
Cpi	0.213***	0.463***	0.643***	1		
Int	0.453	0.243	0.543	0.143	1	
kap	0.473***	0.543***	0.453***	0.343***	0.433***	1

Source: Research finding 2024 Note: *** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$

The pairwise correlation among the variables and their respective significance, depicted by asterisks, is depicted in Table 2. The diagonal of the matrix contains a unit which implies a self-correlation coefficient; the correlation between a variable and itself is unity. First column depicts the correlation between the variables and industrial output, and it can be deduced that all the variables correlate positively with the industrial output. However, the correlation between industrial output and inflation is statistically insignificant; all the variables are shown to have an insignificant correlation with interest rates. There is a very weak and significant correlation between industrial productivity and government revenue followed by government spending and the consumer price index.

Unit Root Analysis

Table 3: Unit root test result using ADF and Phillip Peron techniques.

Variable	Phillips-Perron		AugDickey-Fuller		
	level	first-diff.	level	first-diff.	Remarks
log(ind)	-0.776	-5.249***	-0.638	-7.302***	$I(1)$
	-2.358	-5.066***	-2.530	-6.142***	$I(1)$
log(govr)	-1.605	-6.140***	-1.458	-5.193***	$I(1)$
	-0.533	-6.937***	-0.517	-4.334***	$I(1)$
log(gove)	-3.741	-8.718***	-3.422	-4.318***	$I(1)$
	-2.591	-9.449***	-3.159	-6.812***	$I(1)$
log(cpi)	-1.432	-7.454***	-1.534	-2.016***	$I(1)$
	-0.659	-7.720***	-0.332	-5.843***	$I(1)$
log(int)	-1.475	-2.924***	-1.434	-6.665***	$I(1)$
	-0.321	-2.971***	-1.065	-5.877***	$I(1)$
log(kap)	-2.308	-5.683***	-2.203	-6.084***	$I(1)$
	-2.263	-5.869***	-2.920	-7.286***	$I(1)$

Note: *** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$

Source: Research finding

Table 3 shows both the Phillips-Perron and the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test results. The tests show that all the variables have unit roots. However, at the first difference, all become stationary.

The integrated nature of the variable suggests the adoption of the SVEC as the estimating technique. On the lag length selection, both the AIC and the HQ select 2 as the maximum lag length and this implies that a VECM or order 1 is appropriate.

Cointegration Test Analysis

Table 4: Cointegration tests result

Variable	Test category	Data trend;				
		None	None	Linear	Linear	Quadratic
y, t, g, p, r, k	constant	no	Yes	Yes	yes	yes
	trend	no	no	No	yes	yes
	Trace	4	4	2	3	1
	Max-Eig.	3	3	3	12	1

Note: MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) and variables (y, t, g, p, r, k) represent the variables in Table 4.

Source: Research finding

The results of the test are based on a 5% significance level and the assumptions stated are summarized in Table 4. The results of the Trace and the Maximum Eigen test suggest that the Trace statistic is more robust than the Maximum-Eigen statistics (Lütkepohl & Kratzig, 2005).

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Table 5: VEC model Long-run and short-run adjustment coefficient estimates

Long-run Estimates (Beta Matrix)						
	IND (y)	GOVR (t)	INT(r)	GOVE (g)	CPI(p)	KAP (k)
β_1	1			-0.007 (0.033)		-0.332*** (0.040)
		1		-1.525*** (0.128)		
			1		-0.133* (0.070)	
Adjustment Estimates (alpha Matrix)						
α	IND (y)	GOVR (t)	INT(r)	GOVE (g)	CPI(p)	KAP (k)
	-0.413*** (0.152)	-0.703 (0.695)	0.777 (0.492)	-0.437 (0.481)	0.233 (0.296)	0.887*** (0.286)
	0.051 (0.034)	-0.368** (0.157)	-0.150 (0.111)	0.189* (0.109)	-0.058 (0.067)	-0.143** (0.065)
	0.142*** (0.038)	0.601*** (0.174)	-0.450*** (0.123)	0.347*** (0.121)	0.197*** (0.074)	0.146** (0.072)

Source: Research finding 2024, () contains the standard error, *** p < 0.01; ** p < 0.05; * p < 0.1

Table 5 displays the long-run estimates, and the adjustment estimates. The long-run estimates depict the three identified long-run relationships. The first row of the beta

matrix shows the output-government-spending-capital long-run relationship; government spending is a special form of capital by the government hence this long-run relationship conceptually depicts the output and capital relationship. However, the result shows that the coefficient of government spending (g) is insignificant. The implication is that government investment has not been contributing to the growth of the industrial sector over the years. Government spends its revenue in other sectors of the economy which does not have direct effect on industrial sector growth. Hence, does not stabilize the Nigerian industrial sector. Physical capital (k) on the other hand, significantly impact the industrial output; a one percent increase in the level of physical capital formation averagely increased industrial output by about a 0.33%. this result is in line with the study of Agu & Nyatanga (2020) who found a positive relationship between capital formation and output growth in Nigeria.

The second beta row shows the estimated long-run relationship between government revenue and expenditure i.e. the solvency rule. The estimated result shows that government expenditure significantly impacts government revenue; a one percent increase in government expenditure, averagely increases government revenue by about a 1.53%. This result supports the result of Abdulrasheed (2017). This result passes the 'solvency rule'. The economic implication is that government expenditure can conveniently be financed by government revenue. In the long-run also, the CPI significantly impact the interest rate with a 10% level, a one percent rise in the general price level brings about a 0.13% rise in the rate of interest. This result is in line with Abdulrasheed (2017) who found a positive relationship between inflation and interest rate in Nigeria.

The adjustment estimates (alpha coefficient matrix) shows that the output-expenditure-capital relationship significantly impact the short-run movement of industrial sector output and physical capital only. Also, the revenue-expenditure relationship significantly affects the short-run movement of revenue and capital only. However, the case of interest rate and price equilibrium relation is different, as it significantly impacts the short-run movements of all the variables in the model. It can be deduced from the industrial output alpha vector that about 41.3% of industrial sector output shortage is corrected within a year and the interest rate diverges off its steady state by about 14.2% within a year when industrial output falls below its steady state.

Also in the adjustment estimates, about 36.8% of government revenue shortage is corrected in a year and the interest rate diverges off its steady state by about 60.1% within a year when the government revenue falls below its steady state. Also, the interest rate alpha matrix reveals that about 45% of the interest rate disequilibrium is corrected within a year when it falls below its steady state. In the vector adjustment mechanism, the government spending and the general price level (consumer price index) are shown to diverge away from the system equilibria. However, physical capital responded to the three equilibria points by adjusting towards the revenue-spending long-run relationship by 14.3% within a fiscal year and diverging off the other two equilibria; output-spending-capital and interest-price long-run relationships, by 88.7% and 14.6% within a year.

The study now veered to the analysis of the Industrial Sector Output and Fiscal Policy Shocks in Nigeria employing Equation 6. Figure 1 shows the SVEC model impulse response function (IRF) with a 95% confidence interval. The first row displays the reaction of output to the system shocks, and the subsequent rows show the reactions of government revenue, interest rate, government expenditure, consumer price index, and capital to the system shock sequentially.

The IRF shows that the industrial output reacts positively to the aggregate supply shock. The effect of the shock is permanent and insignificant after the second period. The reaction of the industrial output to the revenue shock is positive and significant, reaching the peak in the first period and gradually declined until the third period. This result is theoretically consistent with the Laffer (1981) effect which noted that a tax rate increase will also increase output to a point where further increase in tax rate will lead to a decline in output.

SVEC model IRF with 95% bootstrapped Hall Percentile confidence

The result in Figure 1 shows that monetary policy shock to interest rate brings a significant negative impact on industrial output, corroborating Yunanto & Medyawati (2020). Also, industrial output reacts positively to government expenditure shock, but the effect is insignificant, corroborating Blanchard & Perotti (2002), Giordano et al. (2007), and Attahir (2016) who found that output reacts positively to government expenditure shock. Aggregate demand shock to price cause a fall in the industrial sector output; this substantiates the macroeconomic theory that a rise in the general price level leads to a fall in the aggregate demand in the short run. However, Yunanto and Medyawati (2020) noted that industrial output responds positively to price shock; the inference is that such an economy is buoyant and inflation serves as an incentive for production expansion. Investment shock to capital shows a significant and persistent rise in industrial sector output, suggesting that a better and more profitable investment opportunities can lead to more capital acquisition.

In addition, the result shows that both government revenue and government expenditure react positively and significantly to positive aggregate supply shock to industrial sector output. The implication is that increases in the industrial sector output increases tax bases which brings more revenue to the government. The revenue generated will be used in the provision of industrial growth-driven infrastructures, thus leading to economic progress. Finally, government expenditure shock increases government revenue while government revenue reacts negatively to government expenditure shock; though both shock impacts are insignificant. This implies that revenue and spending urgency decisions should be taken independently by the Nigerian government. This corroborates Ravnik and Zilic (2011) who noted that government revenue shock has a permanent increase effect on government expenditure but government revenue failed to respond to government expenditure shock.

Figure 1: SVEC model IRF with 95% bootstrapped Hall Percentile confidence

Source: Research finding

The study now goes to the *SVEC model forecast error variance decomposition (FEVD)*.

Table 6: SVEC model forecast error variance decomposition

Proportions of forecast error in <i>y</i> accounted for by; forecast horizon						
	IND (y)	GOVR (t)	INT(r)	GOVE (g)	CPI(p)	KAP (k)
1	0.09	0.09	0.13	0.00	0.47	0.21
2	0.14	0.09	0.06	0.00	0.42	0.29
5	0.27	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.34	0.34
10	0.33	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.29	0.35

Proportions of forecast error in <i>t</i> accounted for by; forecast horizon						
	IND (y)	GOVR (t)	INT(r)	GOVE (g)	CPI(p)	KAP (k)
1	0.37	0.60	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02
2	0.62	0.35	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01
5	0.86	0.11	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00
10	0.93	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01

Source: Research finding, 2024.

Table 6 shows the structural forecast error variance decomposition. This result mirrors the results of the IRF and VEC model Long-run and short-run adjustment coefficient estimates.

Post-Estimation Tests: Residual Analysis and Stability Analysis

The two major post-estimation tests that were carried out in the empirical section are the residual-based and the parameter stability test. The residual-based tests are the test for autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity while the stability test is the recursive coefficient test. The Lagrangian multiplier (LM) test type was used to test for both autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity in the VEC model. The recursive coefficient was used to investigate the stability of the coefficient of adjustment parameters (error correction terms).

Table 7: VEC model post-estimation diagnostic test results

	statistics	p-value
LM test	47.083	0.1022
Heteroscedasticity test	483.33	0.801
Jarque-Bera normality test	2.794	3.556

*** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$

Source: Research finding, 2024

In Table 7, the LM test was adopted to jointly test the incidence of autocorrelation in the VEC models' estimated residuals, and its test against the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation of errors. Also, the study carried out a joint test for heteroscedasticity and null hypothesis of homoscedasticity. Based on the computed statistics and their

respective probabilities, the study accepted the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation of errors. There is no evidence of homoscedasticity of residuals, and the residuals are normally distributed. It can thus be inferred that the results of the SVEC model are viable and stable.

V. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the empirical analyses, this study concluded that Government expenditure fails to stabilize the industrial sector output in Nigeria. This implies that government expenditure does not significantly impact the growth of the industrial sector in Nigeria. This effect arises due to inefficiencies in spending, corruption, or crowding out of private investment in Nigeria. There is an indication of fiscal sustainability in Nigeria over the past four decades. This was shown by the debt-to-GDP ratio that was low, as rising ratio may indicate unsustainable fiscal policies. Secondly, low fiscal deficit and low deficit can lead to debt sustainability. The Nigerian industrial sector output reacts positively to government revenue shock and with an effect that only lasted for a very short run. The government spending shock has non-significant impact on the Nigerian industrial sector output growth. This is unexpected; however, this may be a reflection that most of the generated funds that were supposed to be used to enhance industrial sector growth were put to other uses. Fiscal policy shock to government revenue and expenditure were not significant determinants of the variation in the Nigerian industrial sector growth in the short and long run. Apart from the aggregate supply shock, aggregate demand shock to general price and investment shock to capital formation are the major determinants of Nigerian industrial sector growth variation in the short, medium, and long runs. Inflation (CPI) is one of the motivational factors for productivity. Capital is a significant determinant of industrial sector growth in Nigeria and investment shock to capital has a positive and persistent influence on the industrial sector output. Monetary policy shock to interest rate has a negative and transitory impact on the industrial sector output. The study therefore recommended that economically friendly fiscal policies be implemented for a conducive business environment and for the Nigerian industrial sector to experience growth. The revenue generated should be channeled to the real sectors of the economy to enhance industrial output growth. Monetary authorities may manage inflation and interest rates within the threshold that will enhance productivity in industrial sectors.

Possible Area of Future Research

Further studies may focus on disaggregated perspectives of government expenditure, such as Capital expenditure on the industrial sector of the economy, as this study deals on aggregative perspective.

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